

Leveraging Brand Value for Sustainable Competitive Advantage

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Abstract

A Brand is the intangible sum of a product's attributes, its name, packaging and price, its history, its reputation, and the way it is advertised. – David Ogilvy.

Every successful brand has managed to communicate its company's core beliefs and attitudes—what the company stands for—to its target customers. Brands allow you to clearly define and communicate what you stand for, whether you're the “lowest-cost provider,” the “most innovative,” the “best total solution,” the “preferred choice” and so on.

Building and maintaining distinctive, recognizable brands has ever been more crucial. Faced with fewer blockbusters in the pipeline, increasingly crowded therapy areas and the onslaught of more savvy and aggressive entrants (and also existing), companies are recognizing the need to take a more strategic and rigorous approach to not only developing and maintaining new brands, but also to maintaining and evolving established brands for maximum sustainable competitive advantage.

Because of its importance to the long-term success of firms, marketers have emerged which addresses the content of sustainable competitive advantage (with brand) as well as its sources and different types of strategies that may be used to achieve it.

The purpose of this paper is to trace the significance of branding to attain sustainable competitive advantage and discuss how it has been applied to firms' strategy. It is cites examples of how organizations today paying much attention to managing brands and leveraging on them. It is based on secondary data and literature study.

Key Words: Brand Value, Sustainable Competitive Advantage (SCA), And Competitive Environment

Introduction

Brand names and images are a major element of competitive positioning-often the key to differentiation and sustainable competitive advantage (enhanced cash flows, greater customer loyalty, faster adoption of brand extensions, and more).

Brands are important "strategic assets." Unfortunately, current accounting practices do not treat brand and customer relationships as "investments," and tend to marginalize the value of brands. This seminar will provide important tools and demonstrate how brand and market investments drive shareholder value by enhancing cash flows and reducing risks and vulnerability of business products and services¹.

- **Dr. Rajendra Srivastava***

As the business environment becomes increasingly hostile, more and more companies are discovering the value of brand as a strategic asset and a source of competitive advantage. According to a study by the consulting firm Brand Finance², nearly 72% of shareholder value is tied to intangible assets. And in most cases, brands are the most significant intangible assets.

Traditionally, companies have enjoyed an enviable position where they were faced with little competition. But in an increasingly competitive arena, these traditional

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both traditional and non-traditional players. Due to increased competition, product or service innovations have ceased to be a sustainable source of differentiation. In such

¹ Cited in 'Managing Brand Equity in Business Markets Seminar'

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² The world's leading independent brand valuation and marketing metrics consultancy.

a scenario, competition often revolves around price, thus depressing the margins for all the players in the industry.

In such a scenario, brands can serve as an important means of differentiation and sustainable competitive advantage. Now, in every industry we find marketers are exercising to build strong brands. A consumer research done by Interbrand, the leading brand management consultancy, in mid 1999, revealed that only two financial services firms- Citigroup and American Express Co., figured in a list of world's 60 best-known brands. A similar study by Booz Allen Hamilton³ studied the measures of brand strength and brand recognition. It was found that while brands such as Sears and Coca-Cola were recognized by 94% of the surveyed group, and financial services brands were recognized by only 29% of the respondents.

The traditional business model in the market has been somewhat antithetical to branding efforts mainly because of the perception that brand building is expensive and carries no assurance of guaranteed returns. There is skepticism among companies about the applicability of marketing and branding theory to business. But the value of a company's brand is real. Booz Allen calculated the value of a financial services client's brand equity based on brand related revenues and expenses. The institution's brand equity translated to \$ 4 billion in market capitalization.

The changing market scenario coupled with the value that a brand can generate makes it imperative for companies to initiate brand-building efforts. Their ability to attract and retain customers will now depend upon how fast they can strengthen and communicate their services in the (any) something that is customers: money. important factor decisions. And this is products and services increases the importance of the strong and well-recognized brand plays an important role. Moreover, the increasing brand as a tool for disseminating important information to the customers as well as for attaining sustainable competitive advantage. For marketers today, the strength of their brand

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³ A leading global consulting firm, has more than 18,000 employees serving clients on six continents.

has become one of the critical parameters for differentiation and success. A strong brand influences customer preferences, maximizes return on investments in marketing efforts and strengthens the bottom line. The players, who are able to build and communicate strong brands, will be best positioned to gain substantial competitive advantage in the marketplace.

Brand value and Sustainable Competitive Advantage: Concept

If the ultimate task of an organization is to attract and keep a customer, as management guru Peter Drucker says, and if brands are the ultimate glue, the task of organization has to undertake is to build brand value and strengthen the glue.

Brands have to appear valuable to consumers, to the corporation, to the intermediaries and to a society at a large. Building brand value or instilling the brand with rational and emotional values will make the brand stronger in the eyes of every one.

The idea of a sustainable competitive advantage surfaced in 1984, when Day suggested types of strategies that may help to "sustain the competitive advantage". The actual term "SCA"⁴ emerged in 1985, when Porter discussed the basic types of competitive strategies firms can possess (low-cost or differentiation) to achieve SCA. Interestingly, no formal conceptual definition was presented by Porter in his discussion. Barney (1991) has come the closest to a formal definition by offering the following:

"A firm is said to have a sustained competitive advantage when it is implementing a value creating strategy not simultaneously being implemented by any current or potential competitors and when these other firms are unable to duplicate the benefits of this strategy (italics in original)".

Based on both Barney's work and the definitions of each term provided in the dictionary, the following formal conceptual definition is offered: *A SCA is the prolonged benefit of implementing some unique value-creating strategy not simultaneously being implemented by any current or potential competitors along with the inability to duplicate the benefits of this strategy.*

⁴ SCA is acronym of Sustainable Competitive Advantage

Sources of SCA

Day and Wensley (1988) focused on two categorical sources involved in creating a CA: superior skills and superior resources. Other authors have elaborated on the specific skills and resources that can contribute to an SCA. For example, Barney (1991) states that not all firm resources hold the potential of SCAs; instead, they must possess four attributes: rareness, value, inability to be imitated, and inability to be substituted. Similarly, Hunt and Morgan (1995) proposes, "Potential resources can be most usefully categorized as financial, physical, legal, human, organizational, informational, and relational". Prahalad and Hamel (1990) suggest that firms combine their resources and skills into core competencies, loosely defined as that which a firm does distinctively well in relation to competitors. Therefore, firms may succeed in establishing an SCA by combining skills and resources in unique and enduring ways. By combining resources in this manner, firms can focus on collectively learning how to coordinate all employees' efforts in order to facilitate growth of specific core competencies.

Creating a Brand Value

Brands do not become established or leading over night. Building brand value should be conscious effort, well planned and systematically executed. Thus brand building is similar to building concrete structures. If you observe, all concrete are built systematically brick by brick over a specified period of time and later maintained on conscious basis. Similar analogy applies to brand building, i.e., the marketer should develop, innovate, and add value addition constantly in relation to changing needs and wants of ultimate customers. This explains brand building is an on going process. The brand building exercise has salient steps of various inputs, outcomes and assessments.

Inputs:

- Identification of key customer groups and segments.
- Understanding customer expectations, needs and aspirations.
- Assessing competitive offerings including substitutes.
- Building customer confidence by,

- ✓ Customizing the product
 - ✓ Establishing the key image of a brand
 - ✓ Dealer support – easy availability and push
 - ✓ Innovative communication and promotion schemes, and elegant packaging
- Total brand management – both hardware and software aspects.

Outcome:

- Market share
- New customers attracted
- Customer loyalty index
- Increased profitability
- Brand Knowledge

Assessment:

- Continuous feedback from customers as well as trade channels.
- Scientific inquiry into customer satisfaction determining.
 - ✓ Who is the customer and profile of the target segment
 - ✓ What constitutes customer satisfaction, designing the scale to measure customer satisfaction
 - ✓ Measuring current level of customer satisfaction
 - ✓ Trend analysis and pointers for management of customer satisfaction
- Brand strength score

Laying the Foundations: Sustainable Brand Value

To have sustainable competitive advantage and optimizing the opportunity for the brand comes down to maximizing and maintaining the key brand variables—positioning, personality, brand name and identity. Having a strong brand can ensure a company's long-term success and it also allows companies to earn healthy profits because their brand allows them to charge a price premium. For example, analysts never thought Starbucks would be successful in charging premium prices for a commodity product like coffee. However, the company has been wildly successful thanks in large part to its strong brand management. Strong brands tend to create the longest-lasting competitive advantage. Establishing clear and strategic foundations,

therefore, is fundamental to underpinning the development of any brand. The blueprint of great brands can be seen to meet four key criteria:

- **Relevance.** Understanding the existing brand dynamics of the therapy area, the unmet needs in the market, the hearts and minds of all consumers and customers and target audiences, is crucial to determining the **relevance** of the window of brand opportunity.
- **Credibility.** The paradigm shift in customer power has created a compelling push-pull dynamic, which has forever changed the way in which brands are brought to market. Brand cues and communications, therefore, need to be taken into consideration and be **credible** across all target audiences. Brands need to speak the customer's language.
- **Differentiation.** It is vital that the branding foundations being put in place are defined for **differentiation** vis-à-vis the future brand context, as much as the current brand context.
- **Stretch.** Ultimately, those branding foundations should be sufficiently **flexible**, to accommodate changes in the market and for the post-patent life of the brand.

However, are we opening that window of brand opportunity far enough? Getting the branding right will never compensate for a poor product; but getting the branding wrong, or failing to of a brand, can between good brand and great brand thus impacting on of the difference between good performance and great performance.

The blueprint of great brands can be seen to meet four key criteria: Relevance, Credibility, Differentiation, and Flexibility.

unlock the true potential make the difference recognition and loyalty recognition and loyalty—the bottom line in terms

Increasingly, companies think about ways in which they can start to take ownership of "white space" around the brand in the lead-up to launch, leveraging branding that shapes the perspective of the market. This might include anything from branding a new class of products or services or blend of them, to branding, or indeed, re-branding a condition.

How companies try to attain Sustainable Competitive Advantage: Examples

Today, brand names such as Colgate, Marlboro, Microsoft, Bata, Coca-Cola, Xerox, IBM, and Intel are considered to be among the world's most valuable assets. Brand has the capacity to drive companies through transformation. What GM has done in automobiles, Dell has done in computers and Barnes & Noble is trying to do in publications, are all proof enough of the power of brand to steer a company through changed business equations. Then, there are those seemingly immortal brands, which have achieved sustainable competitive advantage. For these brands, it needn't take magic to buck the current downturn. A look at the recent financial report of Cisco shows the immortality of brands that can connect with the consumers. Nokia has proved that if a brand taps into consumer trends, growth is inevitable and then technological supremacy and first-mover advantage are rendered irrelevant. Following are the illustrations that how powerful brand and branding exercises help companies to achieve sustainable competitive advantage.

1) Colgate — An Iconic Brand

The most important competitive advantage of Company is the brand “Colgate⁵” – an iconic brand that enjoys unrivalled equity with consumers, trade and dental profession alike. The high awareness and familiarity of the Colgate brand ensures speedy distribution and trial of new products under the Colgate brand.

Colgate was once again rated “India’s Most Trusted Brand” for the third year in succession across all brands and categories in an independent survey done by AC Nielsen⁶ for Brand Equity. This reflects the true measure of trust and confidence placed in Colgate by generations of consumers for their oral care needs⁷.

Looking back, the year 2005-06 was satisfactory. Sales for the year have increased by 17 percent at Rs.1,124 crores as against Rs.964 crores during 2004-05. The toothpaste

⁵ Colgate is a brand owned Colgate-Palmolive Company.

⁶ ACNielsen was established in the United States in 1923 by Arthur C. Nielsen, Sr., one of the founders of the modern marketing research industry.

⁷ Statement delivered by the Chairman, Mr. Fabian T. Garcia, at the 65th Annual General Meeting of Colgate-Palmolive (India) Limited held at Mumbai on Tuesday, August 8, 2006.

market grew by 6 per cent during the year and your Company's unit volume grew by 12 per cent, much ahead of the market. This growth was driven by successful new product launches in the toothpaste category and aggressive marketing and branding campaigns of toothbrushes. Three new launches during the year – Colgate Advanced Whitening, Colgate Active Salt and Colgate MaxFresh – helped it consolidate its toothpaste market leadership position.

Reflecting upon the accelerated pace of growth in recent years, one has to recognize that company greatly benefits from Colgate's (brand) truly global presence in over 200 countries and territories, serving hundreds of millions of consumers worldwide. As you know, Colgate enjoys undisputed global market leadership positions in the oral care category. This oral care leadership is mirrored in India. Today, an estimated 450 million consumers in India use the Colgate brand every day. The strong relationship with consumers, customers and the dental profession built over decades of operations in India has made Colgate a trusted household name and the undisputed market leader in the oral care category. Here is highlight of some of the major factors that have contributed to Colgate brand's success in India⁸.

- Deepening Bond with Consumers and Dental Profession
- Innovation and R&D Capabilities
- Distribution Capabilities
- Colgate People

2) Fair & Lovely – The miracle worker

Based on a revolutionary break through in a skin lightening technology, Fair & Lovely was test marketed in 1975 and has been nationally marketed since 1978.

In fact, Fair & Lovely has been extensively tested with consumers in India and abroad, and has been proven to be superior in terms of benefit delivery to all key competitive brands.

Fair & Lovely's formulations contain a unique fairness system that contains a combination of active agents and sunscreens. This has been specially designed and

⁸ Said by the Chairman, Mr. Fabian T. Garcia, at the 65th Annual General Meeting of Colgate-Palmolive (India) Limited held at Mumbai on Tuesday, August 8, 2006.

proven to deliver one to three sheds of change in most people. Also its sunscreen system specially optimized for Indian skins. Indian skin unlike Caucasian skin tends to 'tan' rather than 'burn' and, hence, requires different conditions of UV A and UV B sunscreens.

The fairness cream is marketed in over 38 countries through HHL Exports and local Unilever companies and is largest selling lightening cream in the world. The brand today offers a substantive range of products, including Ayurvedic Fair & Lovely Fairness cream, Fair & Lovely Anti-Marks cream, Fair & Lovely Oil control Fairness Gel, Fair & Lovely for Deep Skin and Fair & Lovely Fairness Soap. The latest has been the Perfect Radiance, a complete range of 12 premium skincare solutions from Fair & Lovely⁹.

3) ICICI Bank¹⁰ & Branded Financial Services

Philosophy:

- 'Trademark customer experience differentiates a bank from competitors offering the same products and services'.
- Service levels must be better than the expectations that are built through marketing and advertising, and then people will talk about your service.
- Touch customers in many ways (insurance, banking, mortgage financing, retirement planning), and through various channels (branch, online, direct mail, telephone etc).
- Catch young customers. Target audience must be youngsters in their twenties with whom it can establish a lifelong relationship.
- Tap into its vast quantities of information about customers' habits.

Brand-Building Exercise:

- Ran a campaign in the print media for educating the ordinary investor; weekly investment articles were published in all major dailies.

⁹ <http://www.hll.com/brands/fairnlovely.asp>

¹⁰ A leading private sector bank operating in India.

- ‘Umbrella’ campaign: Conveyed values of safety, security, and shield against calamities for investors (positioning the brand so as to communicate the value proposition). Used Amitabh Bachchan as their brand ambassador.
- Unified and new group identity for ICICI has been the focus of their branding strategy (a single brand architecture).

First financial services company to brand its bonds offerings: ICICI Safety Bonds. For promoting ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Company Ltd, the theme was ‘cover every Indian with joy, hope, freedom, life’. Further, they chose children from municipal schools who received endowment policies worth Rs. 20,000 each from the MD. Both, the Safety Bond and the ICICI Prudential Life Insurance were programs to deliver the brand promise.

Future Strategy:

- Cross-selling: The idea here is to sell all kinds of financial services through one common channel-selling a Demat account to a savings account customer or selling a credit card or debit card to an existing customer.
- Bundling of services with non-finance companies.

Summary

Services differ from physical goods as they emphasize experience qualities, which can only be discerned after purchase or during consumption.

- Service offering is becoming an integral part of today’s business and in the process of differentiating one’s offerings effectively in the eyes of the consumer, branding services have started playing an important role.
- Building a strategic relationship with the customer is very essential.
- To develop service brands, choose appropriate brand architecture, position the brand, develop the programs needed to deliver the brand and align the business system to the brand promise.

4) Hero Honda Super Brand 2003-2005

Hero Honda brand has been acknowledged to be one of the pillars of the company’s growth. It has been recognized as a super brand in the two-wheeler segment in an automobile industry in India.

Product

Hero Honda's product range is impressively wide – with a model available in every customer segment. From the entry level CD Dawn (with an ex-showroom price of about Rs. 30,000) to the premium image-driver Karizma (with an ex-showroom price of about Rs. 80,000), there are currently more than seven models of Hero Honda bikes in the market.

Based on the purchase criteria, the Indian motorcycle market is divided into three broad segments; In the 'Price' segment the product price is the most important, followed by fuel efficiency. Here, Hero Honda has two brands: CD 100/CD 100 SS and the CD Dawn. In the 'Deluxe' segment, the customer seeks product styling and fuel efficiency. This is the largest segment, making up nearly 55% of the total motorcycle market. Here, Hero Honda has two brands: Splendor+ and Passion Plus. In the 'Premium' segment, power and product styling are the overriding criteria and the customer is less price conscious. Though the third category is currently the smallest segment in the motorcycle market, it is on a clear growth trajectory. For this customer, Hero Honda offers three models: Ambition135, CBZ and Karizma.

Recent Developments

After the emphasis paid by Hero Honda on the factors called 3S (Sales, Service and Spares), the company has now a fourth 'S' added to the list: Safety. At select dealerships, a safety corner has been created, where the customer, who has come to take delivery of his bike, is explained the nuances of safe riding. The company plans to extend this concept to its entire dealer network. In view of increasing product parity, 'soft services' are destined to become the big differentiators. To ensure its continued leadership in the market, the company – among other initiatives – has recently appointed service advisors at workshops, to assist the customers and add value to the service experience.

Of late, the company has also made a concerted effort to increase its reach in the rural market. An important aspect of this thrust was the setting up of 'Service Extensions' in these markets. With this, there are over 1,500 authorized outlets for Hero Honda across India.

Promotion

Hero Honda uses a judicious mix of corporate and product advertising. The corporate positioning is reflected in the base line, 'Leading the Way', while the sales pitch is on an emotional plank, 'Desh ki Dhadkan', a communication that depicts Hero Honda as a part of every Indian's daily life. The product advertising showcases specific motorcycle models. The company has taken an integrated approach to communication and has co-joined its advertising campaigns with sponsorship of sports, CRM programs, direct marketing, as well as the internet.

The company's first advertising campaign was launched in 1984, with the truly memorable promise: 'Fill it. Shut it. Forget it'. This capitalized on the fuel efficiency of CD 100. This punch line became a buzzword across India. In 2001, Passion was launched, with the headline: 'Born in a Studio. Not in a Factory' and a by line 'When Style Matters'. This platform immediately positioned the bike as the best in looks and style. Within four months of its launch, Passion had created marketing history. It had become the second-largest selling motorcycle model in India. CD Dawn was launched as 'Public ka Naya Transport' showing people ready to move from public transport to private transport. It clocked sales of 100,000 bikes within just 100 days of its launch.

Apart from consistent media presence, Hero Honda has been in the forefront of cricket sponsorship, culminating in the sponsorship of the 2003 Cricket World Cup.

The company is a major sponsor of a premier golf tournament – the PGA Asia Tour. Hero Honda is also the 'Title Sponsor' of the annual Indian Television Academy Awards.

Ultimate Brand Values

Confidence and trust are the two enduring values associated with Hero Honda. These values define the bond that Hero Honda establishes with customers cutting across geographic locations, income levels and market segments. The reliability and durability of this relationship has resulted in positive word-of-mouth from satisfied customers, working to the brand's advantage.

The success of the Passport Program among users of Hero Honda motorcycles confirms an emotional association with the company. In a market that has many brands competing for the customers' choice and loyalty, this is a rare occurrence. Its

emergence as a world-leader has also added luster to Hero Honda's image. Millions of satisfied Hero Honda customers take pride in belonging to this two-wheeler 'family'.

Conclusion

In this changing business scenario, none can be sure of a place in the market or who the competitors will be. Finding a response is crucial. New conditions call for new

***Brand is one such
weapon of choice in this
fierce battle for survival.***

ways of seizing and sustaining competitive advantage. But a few business mantras have remained valid even in this tumultuous era. In a seemingly crowded marketplace, with the advent of newer technologies

and emerging market trends, which includes a shift in power to primary customers, or the retailers, the art and science of branding and brand management has much more

relevance than earlier. Marketers all around the globe, with the objective of acquiring and sustaining a comfortable consumer mind-share for their products and services are reinventing the marketing mantras of positioning, branding, and

***Thus sustainable competitive
advantage through powerful
brand is the blazing need for
companies to differentiate them in
a spirited competition era.***

differentiation. At the end I would conclude by writing a statement of A former Chairman of P&G is reported to have said something like *"If all my factories burnt down, give me my people and my brands, I shall have our business back on its feet in a year's time."*

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